

EPR Parameters and Bonding Coefficients in some Copper(II) Bis-thiosemicarbazones

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Epr spectra of copper(II) bis-chelates of some thiosemicarbazones have been described. The epr parameters have been evaluated and used to calculate the MO coefficients. The data suggest strong covalency in the metal-ligand bonds and nearly planar manifestation of the CuN_2S_2 chromophore in these chelates.

THE paper describes epr spectra of copper(II) bis-chelates (1)

formed with the thiol forms of the following thiosemicarbazones: ($R_1 = CH_3$, $R_2 = CH_3$) acetone thiosemicarbazone, $(actscH)_2Cu$; ($R_1 = C_2H_5$, $R_2 = C_2H_5$) diethyl thiosemicarbazone, $(detscH)_2Cu$; ($R_1 = CH_3$, $R_2 = C_6H_5$) acetophenone thiosemicarbazone, $(aptschH)_2Cu$; ($R_1 = C_2H_5$, $R_2 = C_6H_5$) propiophenone thiosemicarbazone, $(pptschH)_2Cu$; ($R_1 = CH_3$, $R_2 = C_6H_5CH_2$) benzylmethylthiosemicarbazone, $(bmtschH)_2Cu$; cyclohexanone thiosemicarbazone $(chtschH)_2Cu$. A systematic variation in the substituents (R_1 and R_2) provides an opportunity to study the effect of change in the alkyl groups on the esr parameters of the copper(II) thiosemicarbazones. The results, however, suggest that the alkyl groups are too distant to have much effect on the nature of the metal-ligand bonds. Copper thiosemicarbazones have been important because of their antitumour¹ and antitubercular² activities. Also, the CuN_2S_2 chromophore forms part of the active site of some copper proteins³.

Experimental

Preparation of complexes: All the complexes were prepared according to the following general method. Aqueous solution of copper(II) chloride was added with large excess of NH_4OH solution. To it was added ethanolic solution of the respective ligand keeping the metal-ligand ratio as 1 : 2. Dark green to black coloured complex precipitated out in each case. It was filtered, washed with water and aqueous ethanol (1 : 1) and air dried. Element

analyses in each case correspond to the composition $Cu(ligand-H)_2$ (Table 1).

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND UV SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		λ_{max} cm^{-1}
		Cu	S	
(A) $(actsc)_2Cu$	Black	19.5 (19.5)	19.5 (19.6)	16 949, 20 080
(B) $(detsc)_2Cu$	Black	16.5 (16.6)	19.7 (19.7)	16 666, 19 047
(C) $(apts)_2Cu$	Green	13.9 (14.1)	14.1 (14.2)	16 666, 18 975
(D) $(ppts)_2Cu$	Green	13.1 (13.3)	13.3 (13.4)	16 863, 19 280
(E) $(bmtsc)_2Cu$	Dark green	13.2 (13.3)	13.3 (13.4)	16 260, 19 493
(F) $(chts)_2Cu$	Dark green	14.7 (15.7)	15.1 (15.6)	16 949, 19 723

Magnetic susceptibility measurements were made by Gouy method using mercury(II) tetra(thiocyanato)cobaltate(II) as calibrant ($\chi_M = 16.44 \times 10^{-6}$ cgs units). All the complexes show magnetic moments corresponding to one unpaired electron as expected.

Electronic spectra (in $CHCl_3$) of the complexes were recorded on a Shimadzu UV-Vis-160 spectrophotometer (Fig. 1).

X-band epr spectra (solution and frozen solution) of the complexes were recorded on a Varian E-112 spectrometer. Typical spectra are shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 1. Electronic spectra (complexes numbered as in Table 1).

 Fig 2. Epr spectra of $\text{Cu}(\text{ohfsc})_2$ in DMF : (a) at RT (.....) and (b) at LNT (—).

Results and Discussion

Epr spectra in solution at room temperature and in frozen solution at liquid nitrogen temperature were tried in a variety of solvents, viz acetone, chloroform/toluene, acetone/toluene (1 : 1), methylene chloride, nujol and dimethyl formamide. At room temperature four line isotropic spectra were observed in all cases (Fig. 2.) The higher field lines show clear pattern of superhyperfine splitting due to two coordinated nitrogens. No noticeable solvent effect was observed. The values of isotropic hyperfine coupling constant are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—EPR PARAMETERS* OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	g_0	A_0	g_1	g_1	A_1	A_1
(A) $(\text{actsc})_2\text{Cu}$	2.075	66	2.14	2.042	166	15
(B) $(\text{detsc})_2\text{Cu}$	2.070	64	2.14	2.085	162	14
(C) $(\text{aptsco})_2\text{Cu}$	2.070	71	2.13	2.040	170	21
(D) $(\text{pptsc})_2\text{Cu}$	2.074	65	2.13	2.046	169	14
(E) $(\text{bmtsc})_2\text{Cu}$	2.074	65	2.14	2.041	165	16
(F) $(\text{ohfsc})_2\text{Cu}$	2.074	64	2.14	2.041	165	13
$(\text{ouktsm}_2)^{*1}$	2.08	88	2.139	2.05	190	37

* A_0 , A_1 and A_1 in gauss. From Ref. 2

which show resonance components due to both g_1 and g_1 features (Fig. 2). The values of the epr parameters evaluated from these spectra are presented in Table 2. The g_1 feature does not show nitrogen superhyperfine structure for any complex. Vanngard⁴ attributed the absence of superhyperfine structure to aggregation of solute molecules at low temperatures.

Kivelson and Neiman⁵ were the first to suggest that g_1 and A_1 are both sensitive to the nature of the donor atoms bound to copper. Vanngard⁴ later compiled g_1 and A_1 values for a series of copper(II) complexes and for some copper(II) proteins and suggested that these two parameters may be employed to define the structure of copper site in the copper proteins. Peisach and Blumberg⁶ did extensive work on the g_1 and A_1 parameters in this direction. They prepared A_1 vs g_1 plots and defined areas for different donor sets for copper atoms on the $g_1 - A_1$ plane. The most important conclusion of these authors is the rule of averaged position. For examples, the region for CuN_2S_2 chromophore is approximately midway between those for CuN_4 and CuS_4 chromophores (Fig. 3). The data-points for all our complexes find place in the region for CuN_2S_2 chromophore. However, our data-points do not exactly

Well-resolved frozen solution spectra were obtained in dimethyl formamide and acetone/toluene (1 : 1)

Fig. 3. A vs g plot (KTS, 2-ketobutylaldehyde thiosemicarbazone, BTS, butylaldehyde thiosemicarbazone; A, B, C, D, E and F as in Table 1).

match with the charge indicated in the plot. Such deviations were noted by Peisach and Blumberg⁶ themselves. Glaring example is that of copper(II)-dimethylglyoxime. More striking is the position of our data-points in relation to copper(II) bis-chelates of butylaldehyde thiosemicarbazone (Cu-BTS) and copper(II) chelate of 2-ketobutylaldehyde bis(thiosemicarbazone) (Cu-KTS). The difference is apparent in the values of A_1 . Our complexes show much smaller values of A_1 ($\cong 165$ G) compared to those for Cu-BTS and Cu-KTS (190 G). Aldehyde thiosemicarbazones evidently form more covalent metal-ligand bonds. This is also clear from the α^2 values (Table 3).

TABLE 3—BONDING COEFFICIENTS OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	α^2	α'^2	β_1^2	β^2	$k \times 10^4$	ϵ'^2
(A) (actsc) ₂ Cu	0.64	0.65	0.63	0.83	91	0.10
(B) (detasc) ₂ Cu	0.63	0.68	0.62	0.66	87	0.10
(C) (aptsc) ₂ Cu	0.62	0.66	0.58	0.76	94	0.09
(D) (pptsc) ₂ Cu	0.62	0.66	0.59	0.88	90	0.09
(E) (bmtsc) ₂ Cu	0.63	0.65	0.60	0.79	90	0.10
(F) (chtsc) ₂ Uu	0.64	0.65	0.62	0.79	88	0.10
(cuktsm ₂) ^a	0.55	0.71	—	—	116	0.11

^aFrom Ref. 2.

The parallel and perpendicular components of g -tensor and the hyperfine coupling constant A are related to the MO coefficients in the following way,

$$g_1 - g_0 = \frac{-8\lambda_0}{\Delta E_{xy}} (\alpha^2 \beta_1^2 - f_1) \quad (1)$$

$$g_1 - g_0 = \frac{-2\lambda_0}{\Delta E_{xy,ys}} (\alpha^2 \beta^2 - f_2) \quad (2)$$

$$A_1 = -K + P[-4/7 \alpha^2 + (g_1 - g_0)(1 + f_1^2) + 3/7 (g_1 - g_0)(1 + f_2^2)] \quad (3)$$

$$A = -K + P[2/7 \alpha^2 + 11/14 (g_1 - g_0)(1 + f_2^2)] \quad (4)$$

$$K = -A_0 + P(g_0 - g_0) \quad (5)$$

$$\alpha^2 + \alpha'^2 - 2\alpha\alpha'S = 1 \quad (6)$$

Here, λ_0 is the spin-orbit coupling constant, P the dipole coefficient, K the Fermi contact term, ΔE_{xy} , $\Delta E_{xy,ys}$ are the excitation energies of the corresponding energy levels, f_1, f_2, f_1^2 and f_2^2 the correction terms, α^2 is in-plane σ -bonding coefficient, α'^2 the out-of-plane σ -bonding coefficient, β_1^2 and β^2 are the in-plane and out-of-plane π -bonding coefficients, respectively, and S is the overlap integral.

β_1^2 and β^2 have been evaluated using equations (1) and (2). The ΔE_{xy} and $\Delta E_{xy,ys}$ have been obtained from the optical spectra (Fig. 1.) The in-plane π -bonds appear to be strongly covalent, whereas the out-of-plane π -bonds are only moderately covalent. The values of α^2 have been calculated from equations (3) and (4). α'^2 has been calculated from α^2 using equation (6). The Fermi contact term (K) is calculated from equation (5). Values obtained are all listed in Table 3.

The values of α^2 for the complexes under study are 0.62–0.64. These values show strong covalency of the metal-ligand bond. There is little change in the nature of the metal-ligand bond due to the alkyl group in the structure 1. The values of the Fermi contact term (K) for these complexes lie in the range $87-91 \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. There are two possible contributions to the cupric Fermi term⁷. First, the metal $3d$ spin polarises the metal $4s$ electron, and second, the spin, delocalised on to the ligand through the in-plane σ -bonding, polarises those electrons which occupy the bond orbital between the ligand and metal $4s$. The total Fermi terms may therefore be given by

$$K = \alpha^2 (K_{\text{core}} + \epsilon'^2 K_{4s}) \quad (7)$$

Rockenbauer⁷ obtained a parabolic relation (8) between K and α^2

$$K = -0.016 (\alpha^2 - 0.85)^2 + 0.0115 \quad (8)$$

and has shown that K has maximum value at α^2 equal to 0.85. The K vs α^2 plot (Fig. 4) has been obtained from equation (7) and it has been shown that the data for copper(II) complexes obtained by all previous workers tally with this plot. Our data for α^2 and K are also in good agreement with this plot.

Equation (7) has been used to obtain the value of ϵ'^2 for complexes. Rockenbauer⁷ gave an empirical linear relationship between ϵ'^2 and α^2 .

$$\epsilon'^2 = 1.06 \alpha^2 - 0.567 \quad (9)$$

This equation holds good if distortion of the local D_{4h} symmetry does not induce significant orbital mixing between the $4d$, $3s$ and $4p$ orbitals. A rhombic distortion of the tetragonal ligand field can lead to $3d-4s$ orbital mixing and consequently to the overestimation of ϵ'^2 from equation (7). In the case of tetrahedral distortion ($3d-4p$ hybridisation), on the other hand, the under estimation of α^2 and so of ϵ'^2 can be expected. The ϵ'^2 vs α^2

plot can thus be used to estimate the deviation of the structure of copper(II) complexes from D_{4h} symmetry. The data-points for the complexes under discussion are quite close to this plot. Evidently, the complexes do not involve any noticeable deviation from the D_{4h} symmetry.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank R.S.I.C., I.I.T., Bombay, for facilities.

References

1. K. LEIBEMISTARK. *Z. Naturforsch., Teil B*, 1950, 5, 79.
2. M. PASZKIEWICZ-GIERULA, W. E. ANTHOLINE, W. K. SUBAZYNSKI, O. BAFFA, J. S. HYDE and D. H. PETERING, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1987, 26, 3945.
3. G. LAPPIN in "Metal Ions in Biological Systems", ed. H. SIGEL, Marcel Dekker, New York, 1981, Vol. 13, p. 21.
4. T. VANNGARD in "Biological Applications of ESR", ed. H. M. SWARTZ, Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1972, p. 411.
5. D. KIVELSON and R. N. NEIMAN, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1961, 35, 149.
6. J. PRISACH and W. E. BLUMBERG, *Arch. Biochem. Biophys.*, 1974, 165, 691.
7. A. ROCKENBAUER, *J. Magn. Reson.*, 1979, 35, 429.